

Paracetamol is the most unscientific and dangerous drug for fever: Anyone can create a fever within hours using antipyretic objects

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Abstract

Paracetamol works in favor of inflammation which is the underlying cause of fever. Paracetamol also destroys prostaglandinE2, a heat-sensitive pyrogen produced by endothelial cells to reduce inflammation and increase blood flow. Paracetamol does not reduce the underlying cause or symptom of fever, disease, or cause of disease, but increases it.

In modern science, one test of whether something is true is whether it can be reproduced. Anyone can create a fever if they are given paracetamol, which increases inflammation and reduces blood flow

The medical book states that paracetamol may cause fever, neutropenia, thrombocytopenia, nephropathy, and skin reactions. This is not a side effect of paracetamol, but its proper function.

If it is said that the medicine used to reduce the temperature of the fever itself causes the fever, the scientific and authenticity of that medicine are being questioned here. There is no science or technology like this anywhere in the world.

Keywords: Prostaglandin E2; Antipyretics; Fever-inducing; Fundamental errors; Fever definition

1. Introduction

Everyone asks what is the scientific evidence when Paracetamol ($C_8H_9NO_2$) is said to be the most unscientific and dangerous drug for fever. This can be answered by correlating the studies on fever after understanding what is the only thing necessary to cause fever and what is the purpose of the fever.

To prove paracetamol is the most unscientific and dangerous drug for fever, it must be scientifically proven that the target of fever is against the action of paracetamol, and that antipyretic treatment is more harmful and suppresses the immune system.

Here we consider the basic contrast between the basic action of fever and the basic action of paracetamol.

No one has scientifically proven that antipyretic therapy, which reduces the heat of a fever, is an appropriate treatment for fever and inflammation. Conflicting opinions on the effectiveness of various antipyretic treatments can be found in various journals.

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2. Fever is one of the least knowledgeable topics in modern science

The science of fever is unknown to modern science. If you read the study reports on fever and paracetamol published in medical books and journals, you will see that the purpose of the fever is unknown to modern science and it is unscientific to give antipyretic paracetamol for fever. Let's look at a few examples:-

- *"The molecular and cellular mechanisms underlying body temperature regulation in the brain remain largely unknown"*¹.
- *"Many fundamental questions about the thermoregulatory system remain unanswered"*².
- *"Our understanding of the neural basis of thermoregulation and fever is still rudimentary"*³.
- *"Thermoregulation is one of the most vital functions of the brain, but how temperature information is converted into homeostatic responses remains unknown"*⁴.
- *"The role of fever in the defense reaction is not clear"*³.
- *"Despite the general usage of the terms 'pyrexia', 'fever', and 'hyperthermia', they are not yet universally defined"*⁵.

Without knowing the purpose of fever temperature and examining what the body does with this heat energy, current fever testing and treatment is based on the belief that fever is a temperature above 100.4 °F and that temperature is harmful to the brain and body. There is no scientific evidence for this belief. But the truth is against this belief.

Study shows that *in hospitalized adults with fever, fever therapy does not reduce mortality or serious adverse event"* ⁶.

3. The only cause of fever and only cause of hyperthermia

The only cause of fever is inflammation. But the only cause of hyperthermia is high heat. Hyperthermia can be created within seconds by using hot objects. It cannot cause fever. Similarly, fever can be induced with antipyretic substances. It cannot cause hyperthermia.

Fever cannot be induced by substances that cause hyperthermia. Fever can only be caused by substances that reduce temperature. Similarly, hyperthermia cannot be induced by cold objects.

Hyperthermia has none of the features of fever.

Hot objects of the same temperature as fever or heat-producing substances cannot cause fever in any living being. pyretics are the only substances needed to cure fever in any organism. Any substance that is hot or heat-increasing (pyretic) is a fever reducer because it reduces inflammation and increases blood flow.

Antipyretics are the only substances needed to induce fever and hypothermia in any organism. Likewise, pyretic are the only substances needed to cure fever and hypothermia in any organism.

Any substance that is cooling or reducing temperature (antipyretic) is a fever stimulant because it increases inflammation and reduces blood flow. We can create a fever and hypothermia within a few hours by antipyretics. Antipyretics cause prolonged infection, which increases death. Likewise, Any substance that is hot or heat-increasing (pyretic) is a fever reducer because it reduces inflammation and increases blood flow.

In hyperthermia, the temperature does not come from the same source as in fever. So there is no similarity between what happens when there is a fever and what happens when there is hyperthermia, and they are contradictory

Since inflammation is the only cause of fever, symptoms, signs, signals, and actions are shown when inflammation occurs. That is why the body hates cold and likes heat during fever.

The main cause of fever in immunocompromised people after being wet for a long time without prior experience is inflammation due to reduced heat energy in the body. Fever is also caused by inflammation due to reduced heat energy in the body when any pathogen attacks.

The body's lack of heat energy prompts the immune system to produce warm substances such as prostaglandins E₂, constrict blood vessels under the skin to conserve and prevent loss of body heat, reduce the firing rate of W neurons that sense heat, and increase the firing rate of C neurons that sense cold.

Similarly, in hyperthermia caused by extreme heat, symptoms, signs, signals, and actions of overheating are shown. This is why the body hates heat and loves cold when hyperthermia occurs. No one gets hyperthermia if they get wet with rain or are attacked by any germs. In hyperthermia, to reduce body heat and lose heat from the body, blood vessels under the skin dilate, increasing the firing rate of heat-sensing W neurons and decreasing the firing rate of cold-sensing C neurons.

Paracetamol is given to reduce prostaglandinE2(PGE2), which increases temperature. Prostaglandin E2 is not a fever-causing substance. It has hyperthermic, vasodilatory, and anti-inflammatory properties. Endothelial cells produce prostaglandinE2, which is an important part of the immune system. The endothelial cells are *the main regulator of vascular homeostasis*.

Any substance that is hot or heat-increasing (pyretic) is a fever reducer because it reduces inflammation and increases blood flow.

The heat of the fever and prostaglandinE2 are the most abundant substances in the body during fever. It is more abundant after the inflammation in the body. They are not abundant before the inflammation. If the fever temperature is reduced by giving paracetamol, substances produced only during fever will increase.

Paracetamol does not eliminate the instruction to form prostaglandinE2. As a result, the immune system produces more prostaglandinE2, when it is depleted.

ProstaglandinE2 is found in the body during fever, similar to the airbag used to protect passengers in a car accident. From this, the immune system produces prostaglandinE2, which reduces inflammation and increases blood flow to the body or organ, making the body or organ healthier and live longer.

Paracetamol, which reduces prostaglandinE2, is given for fever, mistaking this as the cause of the fever. Paracetamol destroys prostaglandinE2, without being recognized by the immune system to increase blood flow and reduce inflammation.

Fever does not go away if heat-producing substances are removed from the body. Fever can only be relieved by avoiding substances that reduce heat in the body. Inflammation is a substance that reduces body heat. All it takes is severe inflammation in the body to cause a fever. The only basic thing needed to cause a fever is severe inflammation.

4. Today's definition, diagnosis, and treatment of fever are fundamentally flawed

In both science and medicine, unseen irrationalities are used in fever definition, diagnosis, and treatment.

Fever includes all things and their functions that increase and decrease only when there is fever.

4.1. What is fever? (Yacob's Fever Definition)

"If essential blood circulation decreases to organs, fever is a sensible and discreet action of the immune system to increase essential blood circulation as a self-defense mechanism of the body to sustain the life or organ"⁷.

The answer to any question about fever can be found in this definition of fever.

In order to sustain life or organs longer, when the existing essential circulation is reduced, a sensible and intelligent immune system has no choice but to produce heat-producing substances and prevent heat loss from the body.

4.2. Fever can be detected by measuring only the objects that occur only in the presence of fever and not in the absence of fever

There is no specific test for fever alone. Today, the same temperature is used to diagnose fever and hyperthermia. High body temperature is hyperthermia. Don't call them fever.

Today's fever tests don't even check for substances like prostaglandinE2, which increase body heat. A proper fever test should check for inflammation and lack of blood flow in the body, which triggers the immune system to produce a fever. In hyperthermia, there is no presence of heat-producing substances in the blood. Diagnosing fever by looking at the intensity of temperature and eliminating the presence of heat-inducing substances in the blood is fundamentally wrong.

4.3. Lowering the temperature will not cure the fever

A decrease in temperature is not enough to reduce the fever, all substances and their functions, which only increase and decrease during fever, must return to the state they were in when there was no fever.

Most people mistake fever for high temperature and take paracetamol to reduce the temperature. Treatment with fever-inducing substances (antipyretic) is the essence of fever treatment today.

Antipyretic therapy is a necessary and appropriate treatment for hyperthermia and not for fever. Lowering the temperature will not cure the fever because raising the temperature is not the fever but the hyperthermia.

Medicines or substances that reduce temperature (antipyretic) can never eliminate fever. Only substances that reduce inflammation and increase blood flow can cure fever.

Therefore, temperature-based diagnosis and temperature-reducing treatment for hyperthermia is never appropriate for fever, and temperature-reducing treatment can cause fever, worsen disease, and cause death.

Today, reducing the temperature of a fever is done by testing and treating hyperthermia, which is the opposite of fever, without a definition that includes things that only occur during fever and without diagnosing and treating only for fever.

According to any scientific law or technology in the world today, the same temperature should not be called fever and hyperthermia. Similarly, fever and hyperthermia, being from opposite sources and opposite to each other, cannot be checked with the same substances and treated with the same substances.

4.4. If the fever is to be cured, all the substances produced only during the fever and their functions must return to their old form

Pyrogens, which raise the temperature during fever, are not the only immune system created.

Therefore, if prostaglandin E2 is reduced with paracetamol and the temperature is reduced, the fever will never go away, because all the substances produced only during the fever and their functions will not return to their old form.

Anyone can create a fever within a few hours by using antipyretics like paracetamol and cold water.

Paracetamol is given to the patient to eliminate the prostaglandin E2 found in fever, just as those who do not know the purpose of an airbag in a car accident disable it thinking that someone will die in a serious accident because of the airbag. As a result, the body swells, blood flow decreases and the patient dies.

Paracetamol does not reduce fever, the cause of fever, morbidity, or mortality, all of which are increased by paracetamol.

Paracetamol destroys all the protective substances our immune system makes when we get sick. It decreases prostaglandin E2, Glutathione, interferon, platelets, WBC, etc,...

Prostaglandin E2 plays an important role in the development of the reproductive system. Researchers have found that paracetamol inhibits the production of prostaglandins E2 by inhibiting the activity of an enzyme called cyclooxygenase, which destroys reproductive cells.

Interferons (IFN) have antiviral, antiproliferative, and immunomodulatory effects.

Some studies have shown that paracetamol has antiplatelet (thrombocytopenia) effects.

Acetaminophen toxicity is the second most common cause of liver transplantation worldwide and the most common cause of liver transplantation in the US⁸.

Anyone can create not only fever and hypothermia, but also pneumonia and death within hours using temperature-reducing substances such as cold water, cold weather, ice cream, and paracetamol. But no one can cause fever, pneumonia, or death by using hot or heat-producing substances such as fire, heat, hot water, and sunlight, which are at the same temperature as the fever. No one can produce hyperthermia with the same temperature as a fever with heat-

reducing agents. But today we see the perverted practice of giving heat-reducing (fever-inducing) substances in the name of curing fever. This is fundamentally wrong.

Paracetamol is the most dangerous medicine for fever for those who have proper knowledge about fever and the action of paracetamol. Without knowing this, paracetamol is a fever reducer for those who firmly believe that a fever occurs when the body temperature rises above 38 degrees Celsius and the fever disappears when the temperature drops.

It is natural for such people to think that it is foolish to see a statement that paracetamol is the most dangerous drug and a fever-causing drug as ignorance knows no bounds. It is not easy to correct their superstition. If they want to correct their superstitions, they should know the difference between fever, the temperature of fever, and hyperthermia caused by heat, what are the substances that make up the immune system during fever, what are their functions, and what activities the body does with the heat energy of the fever.

No one who knows this will never tell you that fever is an increase in temperature, that fever can cause fits and fainting, or that taking paracetamol and sponging with water will cure the fever.

4.5. Fever, hypothermia, and hyperthermia can also be reproduced

One criterion used in modern science to prove that something is true is whether it can be reproduced. Fever and hypothermia can be created by reducing body temperature with antipyretics, but cannot cause hyperthermia. Application with pyretics like thermal heat pad, hot water bag, hot sand bag, etc reduces inflammation and increases blood flow, thereby lowering the fever temperature. Again, with antipyretics like cold water and paracetamol, the body can reproduce the temperature of the fever and hypothermia. Similarly, hyperthermia can be induced by increasing the temperature by applying heat and then reversing the hyperthermia by applying cold. Anyone can test for themselves.

People who don't know what a proper fever is, think that a fever is a rise in temperature, and misunderstand that a fever is gone when the temperature drops, calling temperature-reducing medicines like paracetamol as fever medicines, causing the public to mistake paracetamol as a fever medicine and people use them themselves.

Without knowing the answers to the questions about fever, mistaking the temperature of the fever as a danger, imitating the fever treatment mentioned in the Vedas 1400 years and 3000 years ago, most of the treatment methods are used to reduce the heat of the fever unscientifically. If this non-scientific method of treatment is practiced in the 21st century, it will not be scientific treatment.

Fever definition, diagnosis, and treatment based on speculative ideas are the main culprits in treating fever with antipyretics such as paracetamol and water.

The above statements are the primary underlying matters of fever. Fever is treated with paracetamol without knowing the answer to these primary underlying matters.

Even for diseases that would have cured themselves due to the action of our immune system, using paracetamol can cause inflammation, reduced blood flow, and death.

For decades we have been hearing that the fever has turned into pneumonia. Pneumonia is inflammation of the lungs. According to any scientific law in the world today, fever will never turn into pneumonia. Both are contradictory in nature.

The current practice is to treat the fever with paracetamol and water and turn it into pneumonia. This method of killing does not even deserve to be called treatment.

4.6. Paracetamol to cause and cure fever?

The medical book states that *paracetamol may cause fever, neutropenia, thrombocytopenia, nephropathy, and skin reactions*³.

This is not a side effect of paracetamol, but its proper function.

If it is said that the medicine used to reduce the temperature of the fever itself causes the fever, the scientific and authenticity of that medicine are being questioned here.

Paracetamol is given again to relieve the fever caused by taking paracetamol. There is no science or technology like this anywhere in the world. These fundamental errors have led to the treatment of fever with antipyretic agents. A claim to cure fever by using fever-creating substances is not called a treatment. It is a murderous attempt.

4.7. Is paracetamol an inflammatory or anti-inflammatory?

Antipyretics like paracetamol has been proven worldwide to cause inflammation and infection. Medical books say that *antipyretics cause prolonged infection, which increases death*⁹. This is not a side effect of antipyretics (paracetamol), but its proper function.

*Researchers have found that even a single dose of paracetamol can reduce the levels of glutathione, a chemical in the body that reduces inflammation*¹⁰. Yet paracetamol is classified as an anti-inflammatory. This is unscientific and paradoxical.

Glutathione is said to protect against a wide range of health problems, including atherosclerosis, Lyme disease, Alzheimer's disease, chronic fatigue syndrome, colitis, high cholesterol, osteoarthritis, alcoholism, asthma, cataracts, diabetes, glaucoma, heart disease, hepatitis, liver disease, and Parkinson's disease. In addition, glutathione is purported to reverse the aging process, prevent cancer, and preserve memory.

Fever is caused by the immune system due to increased inflammation. If the antipyretic paracetamol is given to treat that fever and it causes prolonged infection and death, there is no science in the world today that paracetamol should not be given for fever.

Depletion of ProstaglandinE2 and glutathione, which reduces inflammation, can also increase inflammation. These fundamental errors have led to the treatment of fever with antipyretic agents. No such treatment or science was found even in the Stone Age.

4.8. What is the disease caused by taking paracetamol?

Without disease, there is no symptom. If you accept the doctor's argument that fever is a symptom, what is the disease caused by paracetamol and, what is the disease in paracetamol-induced fever and vaccination-induced fever?

Liquid paracetamol is recommended for the baby after the MenB vaccine to reduce the temperature. Paracetamol was the most commonly used drug during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Fever-causing antipyretic paracetamol is given to prevent fever after vaccination.

Antipyretic paracetamol was given to prevent fever after the COVID-19 vaccination. Those educated in the basic principles of modern science would not prescribe paracetamol to cure or prevent fever after the COVID-19 vaccination.

Even those who mistakenly believe that prostaglandinE2, which causes heat, is dangerous, will not prescribe paracetamol for fever. This is because prostaglandinE2 is not produced when there is no fever. ProstaglandinE2 increases temperature. When paracetamol lowers prostaglandinE2 temperature will reduce. Paracetamol is prescribed to relieve and prevent fever without following any scientific rule.

Paracetamol is prescribed for many painful symptoms and ailments. Many ailments like back pain, neck pain, and joint pain are caused by inflammation. Paracetamol given to relieve pain re-inflames the inflammation. Reducing heat-producing prostaglandinE2 will never reduce inflammation, but increase it.

- "It is not clear exactly how paracetamol works"¹¹.
- "It is surprising that after more than 100 years, the exact mechanism of action of paracetamol remains to be determined"¹².

Paracetamol cannot even be classified as a drug for the above reasons.

5. Contradiction is unique to medicine

There are conflicting statements in medical books about paracetamol. Paracetamol can cause fever, cure fever, increase inflammation, and reduce inflammation. Medical literature states that the exact mechanism of action of paracetamol has not been scientifically proven.

Paracetamol has been scientifically proven to reduce levels of prostaglandinE2, glutathione, and platelets. Physicians themselves say that increasing temperature is good and bad and increasing respiration is good and bad as temperature increases.

Physicians say that for every degree of temperature above 37 degrees, 13% more oxygen is needed, and the body uses more energy than when all the organs are working normally, and if the temperature of the fever is reduced, the need for oxygen will decrease, and it is good for the body.

Conductive topical heat treatment of the knees of healthy subjects increased popliteal artery blood flow by 29%, 94%, and 200% after 35 minutes of treatment with heating pad temperatures of 38 °C, 40 °C, and 43 °C, respectively¹³.

Increased blood flow facilitates tissue healing by supplying protein, nutrients, and oxygen at the site of injury. A 1°C increase in tissue temperature is associated with a 10% to 15% increase in local tissue metabolism¹³. This increase in metabolism aids the healing process by increasing both catabolic and anabolic reactions needed to degrade and remove metabolic by-products of tissue damage and provides the milieu for tissue repair.

There are various opinions about whether post-vaccination fever is good or bad for boosting immunity. Some experts say that post-vaccination fever is good for immunity. The second group says it is bad. A third group says people who get vaccinated can expect protection against the deadly coronavirus, whether they develop a fever or not. All of them prescribe paracetamol if the temperature rises after vaccination.

All signs and symptoms of hypothermia are present when fever occurs. But heat treatment for hypothermia will not do for fever. Today in the world, hyperthermia treatment for fever is given without following any scientific law.

We do not find in modern science, in physics, or in chemistry, such a method of contradiction as there is in medicine. Because every object and law is based on these reproducible truths. But in some cases, the medical field is based on speculation and there are conflicting study reports.

So, the so-called experts make contradictory statements about paracetamol such as paracetamol is a fever-curing drug, a fever-causing drug, an inflammation-creating drug, an anti-inflammatory drug, and a drug that destroys reproductive cells, etc. Even those who say this do not know which of these is the ultimate truth. Just because physicians say the opposite about fever doesn't mean the opposite actually happens when you have a fever.

No drug can simultaneously relieve fever, cause fever, increase inflammation, or reduce inflammation at the same time. Similar science or technology does not exist anywhere in the world.

There are few opportunities even to point out this mistake. Even if these prove to be wrong, the old way of doing things has been followed for decades. There is no recognized mechanism to correct or control this. Because of this, any mistake can be justified by those concerned.

Paracetamol is on the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines published by the WHO, contains the medications considered to be most effective and safe to meet the most important needs in a health system.

The World Health Organization should lead the world by keeping modern science at the forefront of health. In order to make an accurate definition, diagnosis, and treatment of fever, it is necessary to know the purpose of the temperature of fever and what activities the body has done with this heat energy. Also, know what is the exact mode of action of paracetamol, as fever and hyperthermia have opposite actions, fever and hyperthermia cannot be checked and treated.

All of the above are basic things to know for proper fever definition, diagnosis, and treatment. WHO cannot prescribe paracetamol to reduce the temperature of fever without knowing these basic facts. Without knowing this, when WHO prescribes paracetamol for fever, it is misusing the name of WHO under the guise of modern science and taking advantage of the ignorance of the general public to spread superstition.

Current antipyretic fever treatment has its origins in the Vedas. The method seen today of reducing the temperature of fever with water is the method mentioned in the Hadith 1400 years ago. In the early days, the treatment was done by religious priests. They follow the treatment of fever prescribed in their Vedas.

It is clear from the above statements how crude and dangerous is the definition, diagnosis, and treatment of fever.

The only solution to escape this dangerous situation is a new definition of fever and testing and treatment according to that definition.

5.1. Is it safe to take paracetamol in the right dose?

The recommended dose is up to 4 grams per day. Researchers found that blood glutathione levels decreased in those taking 500 mg. You can imagine what happens if you take 4 grams. Some patients take paracetamol continuously for 7 to 15 days or more. Even today we cannot rationally decide on the dosage of paracetamol without knowing what is the correct mode of action. Any amount of paracetamol will do the body no good, only harm.

Authoritative medical books say that antipyretics increase inflammation, infection, disease, and death and cause fever, and according to no science in the world today, paracetamol cannot be given to reduce fever.

Do not substitute paracetamol with another drug of the same nature. A fever needs a medicine or treatment that eliminates the things that only occur during the fever.

Paracetamol is given to the patient for many diseases. After reaching the stomach, Paracetamol should be self-identified for which illness it is taken. i.e. to relieve pain, prevent fever, reduce the temperature of fever, etc

5.2. Why can't we figure out exactly what harm paracetamol does?

Because the exact mechanism of action of paracetamol is unknown, paracetamol is added to more than 200 other medicines, it is used for many conditions, and because individuals have different immune systems, it is not known exactly what all harms paracetamol causes.

5.3. Do people die if they take approved doses of paracetamol?

Paracetamol has been used for centuries to treat many people, few of whom die, say paracetamol prescribers. It is difficult to isolate the harm of paracetamol as it is added to more than 200 medicines. Paracetamol causes three types of death and various harms.

- Sudden death
- Death within a few days
- Death within a few years.
- Detoxifies the body.

The use of paracetamol is similar to eating poisoned vegetables, sewage in rivers that collect drinking water, and biting various types of mosquitoes.

No one learns about people who get sick like this. No one collects the number of patients. Apart from these two, it cannot be said that no one will get sick or die from eating poisoned vegetables, drinking polluted water, or being bitten by mosquitoes. Similarly, no one collects data on people who die or get sick from taking paracetamol. No one learns about them. Without both, it cannot be said that no one dies or no one gets sick from taking paracetamol.

5.4. Most of the people who took paracetamol reported that their fever went away when they took paracetamol. Is this correct?

The question is whether these peoples to know what fever is to know if this experience is true. All those who share this experience are those who did not know what is the correct definition of fever and mistook it for fever when the temperature rises above 38 degrees and felt that the fever went away when this temperature decreased.

The only way to change their misconceptions is to understand what the correct fever definition and testing are and what happens when you only have a fever. The reality of the paracetamol experience can be realized if one also recognizes the fact that anyone can get a fever with antipyretics alone. And that fever is defined, tested, and treated as hyperthermia, a temperature greater than 38 degrees Celsius that has no resemblance to fever.

Before reducing the temperature with paracetamol and water you need to know the answers to 4 basic questions.

- What is the purpose of the temperature fever?
- What actions did the body perform using heat, which is thermal energy?

- Who created the temperature?
- What are the reasons and scientific evidence for ignoring the body's messages during fever?

Without knowing the answers to the above 4 basic questions, today paracetamol and water are used to reduce the temperature of the fever.

5.4.1. What is the purpose of the temperature fever?

No medical book describes what the purpose of fever temperature is.

5.4.2. What actions did the body perform using heat, which is thermal energy?

Modern science has not investigated what our immune system does with the heat energy of fever.

Heat has been proven around the world to reduce inflammation and increase blood flow.

There is no fundamental difference between the temperature used in physiotherapy to increase blood flow in arthritis and fever temperature.

Studies have shown that temperatures at the same temperature as a fever (38 to 42 degrees Celsius) can increase blood flow by 27% to 144%⁸.

5.4.3. Who created the temperature?

The source of fever and the source of hyperthermia are not the same. Fever is created by immune system. Hyperthermia is only an increase in temperature due to external causes.

Fever does not occur from a source of hyperthermia. Hyperthermia does not arise from a source of fever. Fever and hyperthermia are mutually exclusive.

5.4.4. What are the reasons and scientific evidence for ignoring the body's messages during fever?

Symptoms, signs, and signals are evaluated in any disease. But no one explains the proper reasons and scientific evidence to ignore body messages such as pain, heat, shivering, discomfort, and skin contractions only when fever comes. Those who cannot understand the meaning of the body's messages during a fever destroy all immune-boosting substances by sponging with water and giving paracetamol.

All living things have fevers. But no creature except man does anything to reduce the temperature of fever. On the contrary, it works to protect the heat from escaping and increase the heat.

Buffaloes lie in water to reduce body heat. Even a buffalo will not lie down in water if it has fever. Most animals lie in light sunlight when feverish. During fever, animals like dogs and cats are found lying in warm ash pits, under sacks, and among the straw. When the fish get a fever, they go there in search of warm water to rest.

When there is a fever, all creatures except humans do not try to reduce the heat of the body, not thinking that they will die, but all creatures have a good sense that there is no other way to save a life. It is seen that they perform actions according to that consciousness or instinct.

When there is a fever, the body resists and hates reducing the temperature. The body tries to warm up again by shivering the muscles. To prevent heat loss from the body, the blood vessels under the skin constrict and like to lie covered. Likes sitting and lying down in a warm place rather than fever. Likes hot water and food rather than fever temperature. The immune system provides all the help it needs to do the above. Ignoring all this, paracetamol is given to decrease prostaglandinE2, glutathione, interferon, platelets, WBC, etc.

6. A technique that reduces fever temperature in 20 minutes

Heat should be supplied from outside the body to the body and inside the body.

Hot bathtubs, steam baths, sauna baths, hair dryers, thermal heat pads, hot water bags, hot sand, and anything else that gives heat can be used to provide heat from outside the body to the body. Each patient should be given a tolerable and preferred temperature.

Warm water, tea, hot porridge, and easily digestible hot food can be used according to hunger and thirst to heat the body from outside to inside. Drink hot water boiled with pepper and ginger. Gargle your throat with warm salt water at a tolerable temperature. Those who apply heat using a hair dryer, thermal heat pad, hot water bag, and sand should apply heat several times until the body is comfortable and sweaty.

When the body sweats when it is heated or it is covered with blankets, or it is steamed, the water reduces the temperature, so the sweaty water should be wiped off with a dry cloth. When the patient feels discomfort, lying in hot water, heating, steaming, and steam baths should be stopped. These should be done only when the patient likes it.

Mechanisms should be made to prevent body heat from escaping. One should sit and lie down in a warm place where the temperature is above the fever temperature. Covering with wool or an insulated dress will reduce the rate of body heat loss.

6.1. A way to get heat from outside the body to every part of the body

Immerse yourself in warm water (tolerable) in a bathtub heated up to 107.6 °F from under the nose to full-foot immersion. As it heats up all parts of the body equally, the temperature of the fever will drop quickly with the increased blood flow.

All living things have fever. A bathtub of the correct shape and size for each animal should be used, and the appropriate temperature should be set for each animal. I discovered a new fever definition, diagnosis, and treatment based on true science .

7. Conclusion

From the above evidence, paracetamol is the most unscientific and dangerous drug for fever, anyone can get a fever within hours with antipyretics, antipyretic treatment for fever is wrong and paracetamol will not help cure fever. Fever is caused by destroying the immune system in any way, fever heat to increase blood flow, and fever needs pyretic treatment, The 20-minute method of reducing fever heat has been self-consistent and scientifically proven by studies on fever without leaving any doubt.

No other illness or symptom is more unscientific than justifying the administration of paracetamol for fever. No disease requires paracetamol to reduce temperature. Paracetamol is also not effective in hyperthermia where it is necessary to reduce the temperature.

So giving paracetamol for fever should be banned as soon as possible. There is no other disease or symptom that is more unscientific than the assessment of fever. The same is true of paracetamol as it is of fever.

If what we say about a subject is incomplete or unscientific, there will be many questions about it and somewhere there will be a gap as if it is not met. But since anyone can recreate a fever with antipyretic substances like cold water, and paracetamol, none of the claims made against modern science about current fever treatment feel incomplete or flawed.

Evidence from modern science is used here to prove that the use of paracetamol for fever and other ailments is against modern science.

There is not even one percent evidence that paracetamol helps the immune system in any way. At the same time, there is 100% evidence that it destroys the immune system. Taking paracetamol for fever is suicidal.

Compliance with ethical standards

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I acknowledged to patients, authors of reference, etc.

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